

Fatigue Damage in Notched, Glass-Epoxy Sheet

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports the results of an experimental study of the fatigue damage originating from a notch in laminated, glass-epoxy panels subjected to cyclic tension loading. The mechanism of fatigue damage consists of the formation of a region of delamination ahead of the notch. The rate of growth of this zone is a function of the maximum stress intensity factor at the notch tip and an inverse function of the number of cycles.

The effects of notch depth, notch root radius, fiber orientation, cyclic frequency and of overloads prior to fatigue cycling were investigated. The residual strength of the panels after fatigue cycling was also determined. Materials were 7 ply laminates of 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$; 0° , 90° ; 90° , $\pm 30^\circ$; and 90° , 0° orientations.

INTRODUCTION

Prior Work

Several investigators have experimentally studied the fatigue process in fiber-reinforced epoxy-matrix composites. In recent years the effect of notches on the fatigue behavior of this class of materials has been studied, often from a fracture mechanics emphasis. Boller¹ and Kimball² were among the first to investigate the effect of notches on the fatigue behavior of glass-polyester and glass-epoxy. Dally et al³ performed tensile fatigue tests on 0°, 90° and 0°, ±60° glass-epoxy panels with side notches of various radius. Waddoups et al⁴ performed experiments and fracture mechanics analyses on graphite-epoxy panels with various center holes and notches for static and fatigue tensile loading. Berg & Salama⁵ studied compression fatigue in unidirectional graphite-epoxy using some fracture mechanics analyses. Mandell & Meier⁶ tested 0°, 90° glass epoxy panels with side notches in tension fatigue and correlated the results using fracture mechanics. Mandell⁷ tested glass-polyester panels in tension fatigue, using woven and non-woven 0°, 90° laminates. He compared crack-propagation rates with fracture mechanics predictions.

Objective and Approach

The purpose of the research reported here is to further demonstrate the applicability of fracture mechanics in describing the fatigue damage process occurring at a notch or similar geometric discontinuity in glass-epoxy composite materials. This information can help form the basis for fatigue and fracture based design criteria for these materials.

Our general procedure is to perform tension fatigue tests of edge-notched, glass-epoxy panels of 0°, 90° and 0°, ±60° orientation. The size of the notch-tip damage zone is observed using transmitted light and the fatigue life is determined for different load and specimen geometry conditions. The damage zone growth and fatigue life for the various test conditions are described using fracture mechanics methods.

TEST PROCEDURE

Specimens

All specimens used in the program were the single-edge-notch, tensile-loaded panel shown in Fig. 1. The only variations in specimen geometry were the depth of the notch, a_0 , and the notch tip geometry. The notches were made with a jewelers saw which produced a notch of about 0.3mm in width with essentially a square end. No attempt was made to sharpen the notch. Five specimens

were tested with a large radius or blunt notch which was produced by drilling a 3.1mm radius hole to serve as the notch tip. Four specimens were tested with a deeper than normal notch, that is an a_0/W of 1/2 rather than the a_0/W of 1/3 used with all other specimens. Load was applied to the specimens through steel end pieces bolted to the specimens as shown schematically in Fig. 1.

The material is E-glass-epoxy manufactured by the 3M Company and is sold commercially under the tradename "Scotchply". It was received from the manufacturer in the form of laminated and cured sheets about 1 m square. The sheets consisted of seven layers of unidirectional material having either of two layer orientation sequences. These are $0^\circ, +60^\circ, -60^\circ, 0^\circ, -60^\circ, +60^\circ, 0^\circ$ and $0^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ$. The specimens were cut from the sheets in two ways, with the fiber direction in the outer layers parallel to the load direction of the specimen, and with the fiber direction in the outer layers at 90° to the load direction. So in reality four different glass-epoxy material conditions were tested. They are referred to in the results that follow as $0^\circ, 90^\circ$ material and $0^\circ, \pm 60^\circ$ material, in which the outer fibers are parallel to the load direction, and $90^\circ, 0^\circ$ material and $90^\circ, \pm 30^\circ$ material, in which the outer fibers are 90° to the load direction.

The specimen conditions described above are summarized in Table 1.

Fatigue Tests

The tests were conducted on a Sonntag SF-1-U fatigue testing machine at a frequency of 30 Hz. Two specimens were also tested on a servo-hydraulic machine at 4 Hz. The minimum cyclic load results in a stress ratio, R of +0.1.

The load was applied to the specimens using a clevis and pin arrangement. This allowed the rotation and realignment of the specimen which occurs with single-edge-notch geometries.

The progress of the fatigue damage at the notch tip was measured by interrupting the tests at various numbers of cycles and taking photos of the notch-tip area. The method used for all specimens was macrophotography at 3X with uniform back lighting, the same basic method used previously⁸. The darkened zone which appears in the macrophotos is the area in which the back lighting is poorly transmitted through the specimen. This darkened area can result from the delamination of one or more of the six interfaces between the seven layers or from the delamination of fibers or fiber bundles within a layer. The type of delamination noted in our tests is described in following sections.

Test results are presented for given values of the maximum fatigue load, P_{max} and also in terms of maximum fatigue stress

intensity factor, K_{\max} . K_{\max} is calculated using the Brown & Srawley⁹ K calibration for homogeneous, isotropic material. Although this material is neither of the above, the degree of anisotropy is such that the stress intensity factor is nearly the same as if it was an isotropic material. In previous work^{8,10} we have taken a similar approach. The isotropic stress intensity factor has been successfully used to describe and categorize the macro-fracture behavior of composites even though it is obviously not adequate to understand the details of the individual fiber or layer fracture process.

Fracture Tests

Tests were also conducted under monotonic loading on a standard hydraulic testing machine. Damage zone growth for these tests were obtained by interrupting the test at various intervals of loading and taking photographs. The data were analyzed as in reference 8 to obtain crack growth resistance curves or R-curves for the material.

Those specimens that did not fracture during fatigue cycling for 1,000,000 or more cycles were fractured under monotonic loading to determine their residual strength.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fracture Test Results

The first tests of the glass-epoxy material were monotonic load fracture tests. Fig. 2 shows the damage zone growth in the 0° , 90° material, photos a, b, and c, and in the $0^\circ \pm 60^\circ$ material, d, e, and f.

Crack growth in the 0° , 90° material is accompanied by extensive delamination above and below the crack. The damage in the 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ material is restricted to a triangular region ahead of the notch with the crack extension tending to be parallel with one or the other of the 60° fiber directions. The more concentrated damage zone in the 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ material is believed to contribute to the lower crack growth resistance in this material.

The crack-growth-resistance curves or R-curves for both materials are shown in Fig. 3. They are calculated using the standard R-curve method, that is, K_R is determined from the load and the total notch-plus-crack extension which occurs at that load. The crack extension measurements are taken from photos such as those in Fig. 2. The points shown from prior work⁸ are for 200mm wide, center-notched panels of slightly different material, 0° , $+60^\circ$, -60° , $+60^\circ$, -60° , 0° Scotchply. These prior results are close to the current, edge-notched results and are slightly lower

as would be expected due to the lower ratio of 0° layers. This good agreement along with the consistency of the data tends to further confirm the R-curve approach for characterizing crack growth under monotonic load.

K values from R-curves can also be compared with critical K values at the inception of fracture reported by other investigators. The K values from the curves in Fig. 3 at a Δa of 2.5mm are 41 and 28 $\text{MN}/\text{m}^{3/2}$ for the 0° , 90° and 0° , $+60^\circ$ materials respectively. McGarry and Mandell¹¹ found a K_c value of $44.6\text{MN}/\text{m}^{3/2}$ in 38 and 51mm wide, double-edge-notched panels of 90° , 0° , 0° , 90° Scotchply. Hamilton and Berg¹² found a K_c value of $16.4\text{MN}/\text{m}^{3/2}$ in 250mm wide panels of 0° , $+60^\circ$, -60° , 0° , $+60^\circ$, -60° Scotchply. Our values compare favorably with these considering that our 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ material has a higher ratio of 0° layers and our 0° , 90° material has a lower ratio of 0° layers.

The fracture test results will be used as a basis of comparison in the discussion of the fatigue results which follow.

Fatigue Damage Zone Results

Table 1 summarizes the fatigue test results. The first group of 12 specimens listed were the tests intended to determine the baseline information on the fatigue behavior of the two materials. Figures 4 and 5 show the typical damage zone growth which occurs in the 0° , 90° and the 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ materials. Photographs a, b and c of each figure show the damage zone, a. after an intermediate number of cycles, b. after the end of cycling and c. after the monotonic load residual strength test. The residual strength loading was stopped before complete separation of the specimen and well after maximum load. Figures 4d and e and Fig. 5d show the combined fatigue damage zone and residual strength damage zone for additional specimens. Fig. 5e shows one of the few specimens which failed during fatigue loading. The photo was taken at 1,000,000 cycles, quite close to failure which occurred at 1,091,000 cycles.

Some general descriptions of the damage zones can be made. The fatigue damage zones in both materials consist of relatively constant shaped, semielliptical regions of delamination or failure of the epoxy bond between layers. Internal inspection of the damage zone reveals that away from the notch only the outer two layers and occasional inner layers have delaminated, whereas, near the notch most of the layer bonds have failed and some fracture within the layers has occurred. The damage zones in our tests were similar to the successive, longitudinal-splitting type of fracture that McGarry & Mandell¹¹ observed in monotonic fracture of 0° , 90° Scotchply and that Mandell & Meier⁶ observed in fatigue fracture of 0° , 90° Scotchply. However, apparently due to the difference in layer orientation, our tests more often displayed

a single longitudinal split and associated delamination zone. The shape of the damage zones can be described by the ratio $s/\Delta a$, referring back to Fig. 1. The typical $s/\Delta a$ values for fatigue damage zones in the 0° , 90° and 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ materials are 15 and 5 respectively. This compares with $s/\Delta a$ values of 6 and 1 for fracture damage zones. This significant difference in shape between fatigue and fracture damage zones is a major factor in determining the fatigue and fracture behavior of these two materials. The transition from the long, narrow fatigue damage zones to the more concentrated fracture damage zones can be clearly seen in Fig. 4d and 5d.

A quantitative description of the fatigue damage zone growth is given in Figures 6 and 7. Logarithmic plots are presented of damage zone size in the direction perpendicular to the load, Δa , versus number of cycles. For most specimens the straight lines shown in the figures are an adequate representation of the damage zone growth. Two exceptions are an apparent upper bound to zone growth in the 0° , 90° tests shown by the dashed line in Fig. 6, and larger than predicted damage zones for the lowest fatigue load with the 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ material, see Fig. 7. We have no explanation for the latter. The apparent upper bound is described in relation to Fig. 8. The expressions for the straight lines on the log-log plots of Figures 6 and 7 are shown in the figures and are repeated here:

$$\Delta a = 8.0 \times 10^{-5} n^{1/5} K_{\max}^{2.5} \quad 0^\circ, 90^\circ$$

$$\Delta a = 8.7 \times 10^{-7} n^{1/4} K_{\max}^{4.0} \quad 0^\circ, \pm 60^\circ$$

Differentiated forms of the expressions are:

$$\frac{da}{dn} = \frac{\text{const}}{n^{4/5}} K_{\max}^{2.5} \quad 0^\circ, 90^\circ$$

$$\frac{da}{dn} = \frac{\text{const}}{n^{3/4}} K_{\max}^{4.0} \quad 0^\circ, \pm 60^\circ$$

It is interesting to note that the above variation of da/dn with K is quite like that of metals; the exponents 2.5 and 4.0 are within the range often observed. However, the variation of da/dn with n is quite unlike that of metals. The $1/n^{4/5}$ and $1/n^{3/4}$ variation of damage zone growth rate in glass-epoxy indicates the growth rate decreases markedly with number of cycles. This was consistently observed in the baseline tests. Most of the damage zone growth occurred during the early cycles and the growth tended toward arrest but never ceased entirely. In metals a constant load fatigue test with the edge-notched geometry used here would produce a continuously increasing crack propagation rate.

We performed fatigue tests to determine the effect of two additional test conditions on the baseline damage zone growth. The tests were 1. with a deeper notch and about one half the load but the same value of K_{max} , and 2. at a slower cyclic frequency, 4 Hz rather than 30 Hz as with all other tests. The damage zone growth data from these tests are plotted in Figures 8 and 9 and are compared with the baseline data shown as solid lines taken from Figures 6 and 7. The damage zone growth in the deep notch tests was not significantly different from the baseline results. This indicates that the size and shape of fatigue damage zones is controlled by K rather than gross or net section stress. The damage zone growth at the lower cyclic frequency was faster for both materials. For the 0° , 90° material the 4 Hz tests produced zones sizes significantly above the upper bound observed in the baseline tests. For the 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ material faster growth and earlier failure was observed in the 4 Hz tests. We interpret this as an indication that the local notch-tip heating, caused by the higher cyclic frequency, limits the extent of the damage zone and thus extends the life of glass-epoxy at high K values. The average temperatures within about one Δa distance from the notch-tip were measured using thermocouples in contact with the surface of specimen 2-10, tested at 30 Hz, and specimen 2-19, tested at 4 Hz. The temperatures near the end of cycling were 41 C and 2 C above room temperature, respectively. The 41 C temperature rise is in the range where Dally and Broutman¹⁵ found a modest decrease in fatigue tests of similar glass-epoxy material. We offer two comments related to this apparent discrepancy. First, notched and unnotched fatigue tests are quite different, so the effect of heating due to cyclic frequency can be different. Second, a loading-rate effect due to the two cyclic frequencies used in our tests may have affected our results. Mandell and Meier⁶ discuss a significant increase in the monotonic fracture strength of 0° , 90° Scotchply due to increased loading rate. Kendall¹⁴ also found an increase in monotonic crack growth resistance of about 15 percent for this variation of loading rate. This type of increased strength due to loading rate alone (and apart from the heating which also occurs in fatigue tests) could account for the better fatigue properties we observed at the higher cyclic frequency. The separation of loading-rate effects and heating effects in fatigue of glass-epoxy is an area which should be pursued.

Fatigue Life and Residual Strength

A summary of many of the significant results from this program are shown in Fig. 10. The number of cycles to failure, n_F , is plotted versus K_{max} for both materials, with the outer layers parallel to the load direction, designated 0° , 90° and 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$, and with the outer layers perpendicular to the load direction, designated 90° , 0° and 90° , $\pm 30^\circ$. Although the tests performed did not establish the fatigue life curves with a high degree of certainty, it is still clear that the glass-epoxy with the outer

layers parallel to the load direction has a longer fatigue life by several orders of magnitude. The much superior behavior of the 0° layer material is also indicated by the one cycle data shown. These data points are the K values from the R-curves in Fig. 3 for the 0° , 90° and $0^\circ \pm 60^\circ$ orientations and from similar plots for the 90° , 0° and $90^\circ, \pm 30^\circ$ orientation. The K values were taken at a Δa of 2.5mm. This value was arbitrarily picked to represent a significant amount of crack growth, and in all but the $0^\circ, 90^\circ$ orientation the $\Delta a = 2.5\text{mm}$ point corresponds closely with the point of maximum load in the R-curve test. Mandell and Meier's⁶ results from fatigue of double-edge-notch panels of $90^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ$ Scotchply are shown as the dashed line in Fig. 10. The lower life is expected because their material has a lower ratio of 0° layers. Their higher K value for one-cycle fracture tests are due to the fact that they performed these tests at a high loading rate to correspond to the fatigue loading rate. The fracture toughness they measured from quasi-static tests was $18 \text{ MN/m}^{3/2}$.

Some understanding of the much lower fatigue life of the 90° outer layer material can be gained from the damage zones of these materials shown in Fig. 11. The fatigue damage zone in the $90^\circ, 0^\circ$ material, the darkest area adjacent to the notch, is considerably more concentrated than those observed in $0^\circ, 90^\circ$ material. The monotonic fracture of the same specimen after fatigue loading occurred with almost no damage zone formation. The damage zones in the $90^\circ, \pm 30^\circ$ material were quite concentrated and essentially the same for fatigue and monotonic loading. These concentrated damage zones in the 90° outer layer materials, as opposed to the long semi-elliptical zones which blunt and retard the crack is a controlling factor in their poor fatigue life.

As previously stated, all specimens that did not fracture during fatigue cycling were loaded to fracture under monotonic load. The results of these residual strength tests are shown in Fig. 12 which shows the maximum load required to fracture the specimen as a function of the fatigue load used in the prior cycling. The maximum load required for fracture in R-curve tests is shown on the ordinate for comparison. The general increase we observed in the residual strength as a function of prior fatigue load is again attributed to the nature of the fatigue damage zone. As mentioned previously, the damage zone is primarily a region of delamination, with little fiber breakage. The high normal stresses and inter-layer shear stresses which normally exist near a notch are relieved and spread over the larger area of the damage zone. Since the damage zones are larger at high fatigue loads, the residual strength is increased. The obvious limit to this increase in residual strength occurs when the fatigue damage zone proceeds far enough across the specimen to cause significant weakening or to cause fracture during cycling as with the $0^\circ, 60^\circ$ material at the two higher loads.

The effect of two additional test variables on fatigue behavior was studied. They are the effect of a tensile overload prior to fatigue cycling and the effect of blunt notches.

The effect of an overload at 1.5 times the load of the subsequent fatigue test had no significant effect on the 0° , 90° tests, see Table 1. However, an overload of only 1.1 times the fatigue load produced drastic changes in the 0° , 60° tests. The life of specimen 3-13 for example, which received a 10 percent overload was more than a factor of 100 shorter than the life of the comparable specimens with no overload. We believe this behavior is quite general in notched glass-epoxy, where very small (such as 10 percent) overloads can reduce million cycle lives by several orders of magnitude. This behavior is quite different from that of metals, where the effect of a 10 percent overload on a million cycle life would often be no noticeable change or an increase in life. The difference is related to the fact that the ratio of fatigue strength to one-cycle fracture strength can be much closer to unity in glass-epoxy than in metals. So the crack growth which occurs during overload of glass-epoxy (and generally not with metals) can cause a large decrease in the subsequent fatigue life. Such a decrease in life was observed with specimen 3-9 which was loaded near the one cycle fatigue strength and is shown in Fig. 13 c and d. The crack growth which started during overload, Fig. 13c, was not very much slowed by protective damage zone growth during fatigue. The result was a short life. In contrast, specimen 2-8, shown in Fig. 13 a and b was cycled further below the fracture strength. Thus a large damage zone formed and retarded the crack growth.

We found no significant effect on the fatigue behavior of glass-epoxy due to blunt notches, that is, due to the presence of 3.2mm radius notches in comparison with the standard 0.3mm wide jeweler's saw notch. The fatigue life and residual strength of the blunt notch specimens were essentially the same as in the corresponding baseline tests. The only difference in the fatigue damage zones was the much reduced damage just ahead of the notch in the 0° , 90° specimens see Fig. 14. The insensitivity to notch sharpness we found in our tests with a relatively deep edge notch is similar to the Dally et al³ results in 0° , 90° and 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ glass-epoxy panels with shallow double-edge notches. They reported relatively small decreases in fatigue life when elastic stress concentration factor increased from 1 to 10. We support their general conclusion that, compared to metals, glass-epoxy is quite insensitive to notch sharpness.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the experimental results reported in this paper, along with results of other investigators referenced herein, we

make the following conclusions. These apply to relatively deeply notched, tensile loaded sheets of laminated, multi-directional, glass-epoxy composites of the general type used in our experiments.

1. The stress intensity factor, K , effectively describes and categorizes fracture in this material. Fracture strength can be determined using the crack-growth-resistance curve or R-curve method. An effective K_c value can be determined for any specific laminate. These values vary from 20 to 40 MN/m^{3/2} with the higher values corresponding to higher percentages of fibers in the direction of loading.

2. The fatigue life can be described by straight lines on a plot of either K_{max} or ΔK (nearly equivalent in our tests) versus logarithm of number of cycles to failure. These lines include the value of K_c at a life of one cycle.

3. The fatigue damage zone growth rate is a function of K_{max} or ΔK , rather than net or gross section stress, and decreases with number of cycles at constant K . The damage zone growth follows the relationship,

$$da/dn = \text{constant} \cdot K^a/n^B$$

where a and B depend on the material. This relationship holds as long as the dimensions of the damage zone are small compared with the specimen dimensions.

4. The fatigue damage zones exert a favorable effect on the fracture of these materials. The presence of such zones may cause an increase in the overall residual fracture strength over that for a specimen which has not been subjected to fatigue cycling. We attribute both the residual strength increase and the damage zone growth rate decrease to an effective notch "blunting" and stress redistribution which occurs as the damage zone grows. This is similar to "notch geometry changes" noted by Dally, et al³.

5. The orientation of the outermost layers of these materials is particularly important in determining the fatigue and fracture behavior. It is important that, in any structural design using these materials, the outermost fibers be parallel to the direction of maximum stress. Cross-ply or angle-ply layers should be located adjacent to the surface layers to reduce the longitudinal splitting of the outer layers.

6. In the interpretation of results of non-destructive inspections of these materials after exposure to a large number of loading cycles, the existence of fairly large, elongated damage zones in the region of stress concentrations should not always be considered harmful. In many cases, these damage zones could

result in an increase in the overall strength of the structure from that before cycling. Conversely, small, concentrated damage zones produced by a high, single loading cycle, such as proof testing can result in significant reductions in fatigue life of a structure.

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NOTATION

- a - Depth of Notch Plus Crack
- a_o - Depth of Sawed Notch
- Δa - Crack Growth or Damage Zone Growth
- K - Opening Mode Stress Intensity Factor
- K_{max} - Maximum K During Fatigue Cycle
- n - Number of Fatigue Cycles
- n_F - Number of Fatigue Cycles at Failure
- P - Applied Tensile Load
- P_{max} - Maximum P During Fatigue Cycle
- R - Crack Growth Resistance
- s - Height of Damage Zone
- W - Width of Specimen

TABLE 1

FATIGUE TEST CONDITIONS AND RESULTS

	Layer Orien- tation	Specimen Number	Fatigue Load, P_{max} kN	Total No. of Fatigue Cycles	Total Damage Zone Δa mm	Residual Strength kN	
<u>Baseline Tests</u> ($a_0/W=1/3$)	0°, 90°	2-2	4.4	1,600,000	1.6	12.3	
		2-3	5.3	1,600,000	2.2	11.4	
		2-4	6.2	1,600,000	3.3	11.2	
		2-9	7.1	1,600,000	3.4	12.5	
		2-10	8.0	1,600,000	3.6	13.5	
		2-18	8.9	946,000	-	-	
	0°, +60°	3-2	4.4	1,600,000	3.6	9.1	
		3-8	5.3	1,600,000	4.8	10.2	
		3-4	6.2	1,600,000	7.8	11.0	
		3-11	7.1	274,000	-	-	
		3-15	7.1	1,091,000	-	-	
		3-12	8.0	308,000	-	-	
	<u>Deep Notch</u> ($a_0/W=1/2$)	0°, 90°	2-6	2.3	1,600,000	2.0	6.3
			2-5	3.2	1,600,000	4.4	6.2
0°, +60°		3-7	2.3	1,600,000	2.7	4.8	
		3-5	3.2	1,600,000	7.8	6.0	
<u>Slow Cycle Frequency</u> ($a_0/W=1/3$)	0°, 90°	2-19	8.0	500,000	6.1	12.0	
	0°, +60°	3-19	8.0	131,000	-	-	

TABLE 1 (CONT'D)

	Layer Orien- tation	Specimen Number	Fatigue Load, P_{\max} kN	Total No. of Fatigue Cycles	Total Damage Zone Growth, Δa mm	Residual Strength kN	
<u>90° Outer Layers</u> ($a_0/W=1/3$)	90°, 0°	2-C	4.4	1,000,000	3.8	6.1	
		2-B	5.3	1,000,000	7.4	7.7	
		2-D	5.3	646,000	-	-	
		2-A	6.2	7,000	-	-	
		2-E	6.2	100	-	-	
	90°, +30°	3-B	4.4	86,000	-	-	
		3-A	5.3	14,000	-	-	
3-C		6.2	300	-	-		
<u>Overload</u> ($a_0/W=1/3$) first cycle at	0°, 90°	1.50 P_{\max}	2-8	6.2	1,000,000	5.7	11.8
		1.50 "	2-12	7.1	1,000,000	7.7	11.7
		1.50 "	2-13	8.0	1,000,000	8.4	12.3
	0°, +60°	1.10 "	3-10	6.2	1,000,000	16.5	7.9
		1.20 "	3-9	6.2	5,000	-	-
		1.10 "	3-13	7.1	1,000	-	-
		1.15 "	3-16	7.1	1	-	-
	<u>Blunt Notch</u> ($a_0/W=1/3$)	0°, 90°	2-7	5.3	1,600,000	1.3	12.4
			2-14	8.0	1,600,000	4.8	12.7
		0°, +60°	3-6	5.3	1,600,000	5.5	9.8
3-14			7.1	1,600,000	14.9	11.1	
3-17			8.0	93,000	-	-	

1. Glass-Epoxy Specimen Geometry.

2. Crack Growth Under Monotonic Loading.

a, b, c: 0° , 90° Spec. 2-15; 9.7, 11.7, 14.9 KN Load, Respectively
 d, e, f: 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ Spec 3-18; 6.8, 6.9, 5.6 KN Load, Respectively 3X

3. Crack Growth Resistance Curves for Glass-Epoxy.

4. Fatigue and Residual Strength Damage in 0° , 90° Glass Epoxy.
a, b, c: Spec. 2-3; 500,000 cy, 1,600,000 cy, (a) fracture
d, e: Spec. 2-4 and 2-9; (a) fracture

3X

5. Fatigue and Residual Strength Damage in 0° , $+60^\circ$ Glass-Epoxy
 a, b, c: Spec. 3-8; 260,000 cy, 1,600,000 cy, @ fracture
 d, e: Spec 3-4 and 3-15; @ fracture, 1,000,000 cy 3X

6. Fatigue Damage Zone Growth in $0^\circ, 90^\circ$ Glass-Epoxy.

7. Fatigue Damage Zone Growth in $0^\circ, \pm 60^\circ$ Glass-Epoxy.

8. Fatigue Damage Zone Growth for Various Loading in 0°, 90° Glass Epoxy.

9. Fatigue Damage Zone Growth for Various Loading in 0°, ± 60° Glass Epoxy.

10. Fatigue Life Versus K_{max} for Glass-Epoxy.

11. Fatigue and Residual Strength Damage in 90° , 0° and 90° , $\pm 30^\circ$ Glass-Epoxy.
 a: 90° , 0° Spec. 2-C@ fracture
 b: 90° , $\pm 30^\circ$ Spec. 3-D@ fracture 4X

12. Residual Strength Following Fatigue of Glass-Epoxy.

13. Fatigue and Overload Damage in Glass-Epoxy.
a, b: 0° , 90° Spec. 2-8; After Overload, 50,000 cy
c, d: 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ Spec 3-9; After Overload, 5,000 cy 4X

14. Fatigue Damage in Blunt Notched Glass-Epoxy.
a: 0° , 90° Spec. 2-7, 1,600,000 cy
b: 0° , $\pm 60^\circ$ Spec 3-6, 1,600,000 cy

5X